

The GloWorm Project: Compiling regional level data to understand large-scale distributions of native and non-native species

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Project Summary

Despite ongoing research over decades, our understanding of the global distribution of species remains limited for all but a relatively small number of species. This lack of knowledge is especially pronounced for belowground organisms, as their global distributions have only recently begun to be investigated. However, similar to aboveground organisms, global distributions of soil organisms appear to be shifting substantially due to human impacts and the enhanced movement of native and non-native species across their natural geographic distributions. Earthworms (Crassiditellata) are important providers of many functions and services that humans rely on, such as decomposition of litter and nutrient cycling. However, non-native earthworms can severely alter ecosystems, both belowground and aboveground. The distribution maps we create will take into account whether each species is native or non-native, and will thus allow a better understanding of how biodiversity patterns change when this status is considered. We will test whether trade routes are the main vector of non-native earthworms, by comparing these routes with the native region of these species. With our analysis of global distributions of native and invasive earthworms, we aim to provide critical information to guide future conservation actions.

Introduction

Human activities are altering species distributions worldwide (McKinney and Lockwood 1999; Capinha et al. 2015). These activities are causing range contractions of native species (Di Marco and Santini 2015) while also driving range expansions of non-native species by transporting them to new regions (Capinha et al. 2015; Van Kleunen et al. 2015). Non-native species can become invasive and impact communities and ecosystem functioning, leading to further effects on native species (Simberloff et al. 2013). However, for many groups of taxa, we lack an understanding of the extent to which species distributions are being reshuffled, as well as of the key factors that determine distributions of non-native versus native species.

Most of our knowledge of species distributions is derived from aboveground organisms, despite the finding that belowground organisms do not necessarily follow the same patterns at large scales (Tederloo et al. 2014; Cameron et al. 2019; van den Hoogen et al. 2019). Furthermore, of the global diversity maps that have been created for soil organisms, most have not clearly distinguished between native and non-native species (e.g., Tederloo et al. 2014; Phillips et al. 2019; van den Hoogen et al. 2019). Given the functional and economic importance of soil biodiversity and the tight linkages between aboveground and belowground systems (Wardle et al. 2004), an understanding of distributions of belowground species globally is critical for effective management of communities and ecosystems.

Earthworms (Crassiditellata) are relatively well-studied globally as compared to other soil taxa. Around 120 species (out of a total of >6000 species) have invaded new regions (Hendrix et al. 2008;

Anderson et al. 2017), making them an ideal group for investigating large-scale biodiversity patterns and belowground invasions. In addition, earthworms act as crucial ecosystem engineers and key detritivores in many terrestrial ecosystems (Blouin et al. 2013). In recently deglaciated regions in Canada and the northern United States, the introduction of non-native earthworm species to forests has resulted in a range of impacts such as cascading negative effects on plants and other soil organisms (Frellich et al. 2019).

Our working group will investigate global distributions of native and non-native earthworms. We will create the first global species-level map of non-native vs. native earthworm distributions to quantify the extent of earthworm invasions worldwide and identify the country of origin (source) of the non-native species.

Current and future methods

Initial country-level lists

During 2020, we created country-level lists of earthworm species for each of the 195 countries recognised by the United Nations. These initial lists were created using two approaches, firstly by extracting data from DriloBASE (<http://taxo.drilobase.org/>), and secondly by undertaking comprehensive literature searches. This two-step approach ensured that all recent literature was included in each country list.

Each country-level list included scientific name (binomial, as well as genus and family name) of each earthworm present, as well as descriptions of their regional distribution, their ecological category (e.g., epigeic, endogeic, anecic) and whether they were native or not to the country (and if non-native, the geographic region they originate from).

Review of country-level lists

As not all species descriptions have been published, not all published papers are in English or published in internationally available journals, and in-country taxonomists' knowledge will be greater than what is publicly available, where possible each country-level list is being reviewed by an earthworm taxonomist from (or very familiar with) the country.

During this review process, the taxonomists are ensuring that all species they know are present in the country are listed, as well as resolving taxonomic issues (e.g., synonymous species names), and further identifying whether each species is native to the country or not. To ensure transparency in all the data that is compiled, references are provided for all information. This process is proving very important and informative, as many of the country-level lists of earthworms were either incomplete, incorrect or contained duplicated species due to synonyms.

Modelling of large-scale distributions of earthworms

This dataset will allow us to understand regional-level patterns of earthworm diversity, and the difference between native and non-native patterns. As well as understanding the country-level distribution of non-native earthworm species, we will investigate the potential factors (e.g., climate, geographical barriers, land uses, trade routes) that are driving their expansion. We hypothesize that transport of earthworms along trade routes has allowed earthworms to spread into previously uninhabited areas, thus expanding distributions of non-native species (Capinha et al. 2015). In particular, we expect that trade routes that were historically important will be a stronger driver of distributions than more recent trade routes (Beauséjour et al. 2015). For this analysis, we plan to use

data from the HYDE 3.1 database on human populations and land use (Klein Goldewijk et al. 2011), trade data from the Correlates of War project (Barbieri et al. 2009), and CHELSA climate data (Karger et al. 2017), and potentially other datasets.

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We are working with over 80 taxonomists across the globe to create this dataset, and we thank them all for their time and dedication.

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Note: This document has not been peer-reviewed, but has been produced to provide background information to this on-going project.